

Outlier Accommodation in Censored Time Series

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Abstract

When estimating trends in contaminated media, it is common to jointly observe apparent outliers *and* non-detects (i.e., left-censored observations). Accurately identifying outliers usually favors de-trending the time series prior to screening for outlying residuals. This screening in turn requires a reference distribution from which to judge outlying points.

The combination of censored data, nonlinear trends, and outliers is challenging: 1) how to estimate the trend prior to treating non-detects, and vice-versa? 2) how to compute ‘censored residuals’ from the trend? 3) how to build a reference distribution given substantial censoring?

We previously proposed a Monte Carlo mixture model that samples non-detects from a class of bounded distributions on the interval $(0, RL)$, where RL is a left-censoring limit. We present a new algorithm called **Monte Carlo Outlier IDentification** (MCOID) using this mixture model that can accurately identify outliers by constructing a broad trend using the mean estimate of repeated draws from the mixture model, and studentizing the trend residuals to both flag and down-weight outliers via an appropriate kernel applied to the studentized distance from the trend.

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1 Introduction

When estimating trends in potentially contaminated environmental media (e.g., soil, groundwater), it is common to jointly observe apparent outliers *and* non-detects (i.e., left-censored observations or NDs). Typical environmental statistical analysis consists of identifying outliers based on adhoc univariate rules (e.g., more than 2-3 standard deviations from the mean) while mostly ignoring the presence of censoring (e.g., taking NDs at ‘face value’ or perhaps at half the reporting or detection limit [RL]). More sophisticated outlier treatments generally rely on univariate methods, e.g., Rosner’s test (**Rosner, 1975**), Dixon’s test (**Barnett & Lewis, 1994**), Tukey’s box plot screening (**Tukey, 1977**), or other tests of discordancy.

But identifying outliers in time series usually favors de-trending the time series prior to screening for outlying residuals. This screening, in turn, requires a reference distribution from which to judge outlying points. Local changes in the trend may cause values consistent with the trend to appear or test as outliers, thus resulting in misclassification. Misclassification also occurs when local outliers (relative to the trend) are ‘missed’ by univariate outlier screening.

The combination of (left-)censored data, nonlinear trends, and outliers presents multiple challenges:

- how to estimate the trend prior to treating/adjusting for non-detects, and vice-versa?

- how to compute ‘censored residuals’ from the estimated trend?
- how to build a reference distribution under substantial censoring?
- how to accommodate irregular time series data (i.e., non-uniform temporal spacing)?

We offer a practical strategy – **Monte Carlo Outlier IDentification (MCOID)** – to meet these challenges. MCOID more accurately identifies probable outliers and lessens misclassification rates, especially in the presence of left-censored data.

2 Method

In previous work on environmental non-detects, we proposed a Monte Carlo mixture model that draws sample estimates for non-detects from a class of bounded distributions on the interval $(0, RL)$, where RL is a left-censoring limit that may vary by observation (**Cameron, 2019**). Distributions included the uniform, triangle, and a series of beta densities. Empirical testing indicated that the Monte Carlo mixture model, when estimating summary statistics, compared favorably to other common environmental data censoring adjustments (e.g., Kaplan-Meier, regression on order statistics [ROS], simple substitution) (**USEPA, 2009**).

This mixture model can be extended to any statistical estimate, including time series trends. MCOID first involves constructing a low dimensional Monte Carlo-based estimate designed only to capture broad changes in the trend while ignoring influence from possible outliers. The algorithm does this as follows:

- For each of a series of Monte Carlo draws designed to impute any non-detects, we construct a broad natural spline trend estimate and associated prediction band (using 2-7 knots, with final fit chosen via automated leave-one-out cross-validation). This trend estimate is fit to the time series represented by the joint set of detected values (‘detects’) and imputed non-detects.
- The spline trends and prediction bands are averaged point-wise across the Monte Carlo draws to derive the final estimate. A typical computer using R can run a reasonable set of draws and quickly build a trend estimate (\ll 1 sec).
- To minimize influence on the trend from any outliers, the spline fit is constructed *after* applying a first-pass running medians smoother to the time series.

We next compute (approximate) externally studentized trend residuals (**Draper & Smith, 1998**) using the *nominal* value of each observation (for non-detects, the nominal value is the detection or reporting limit, i.e., the left-censoring threshold).

The standard error (s_e) of the spline is computed via the mean square of the residuals from the final trend estimate:

$$s_e^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n e_i^2 / \text{df} = \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 / \text{df}$$

where df is the residual degrees of freedom of the trend. The externally studentized residual distance of the i th observation is computed as:

$$t_i = (y_i - \hat{y}_i) / s_{-i} (1 - h_{ii})^{1/2}$$

where

$$s_{-i}^2 = \frac{(n-2)s_e^2 - (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 / (1 - h_{ii})}{n-3}$$

is an estimate of the overall variance after deleting the contribution due to the i th trend residual, and h_{ii} is the i th diagonal element of the ‘hat’ matrix H . The studentized residuals t_i thus attempt not only to account for the leverage of the point being estimated, but also to avoid bias in the variance estimate due to outlying deviations from the trend.

Use of the nominal value for each non-detect (rather than the Monte Carlo imputations) allows identification of ‘censored’ outliers, i.e., cases where an atypically high detection/reporting limit has been assigned by the analytical lab (often due to repeated chemical sample dilutions). External studentization limits the impact of outliers on the residual variance, leading to larger studentized residuals. In general, the studentization is approximate, since the trend is non-linear instead of linear; this in turn impacts the appropriate reference distribution for the studentized residuals.

To classify observations as possible or probable outliers, we examine their studentized distance from the spline estimate. For non-linear trends, an appropriate reference distribution for the trend residuals is unknown. In the linear case with normal errors, externally studentized residuals follow a Student’s t with $(n-3)$ df (**Draper & Smith, 1998**). Complicating matters, variability in environmental time series accrues from multiple co-contributing and potentially independent stochastic processes, including fluctuations in the (contaminated) source and in-situ (i.e., natural or pre-existing) variation, field handling variability (i.e., physical sampling, collection, and storage techniques), and laboratory/analytical measurement variation.

Empirical testing suggests an assumption of normal errors is rarely credible. Real datasets typically exhibit larger degrees of kurtosis, so that reference distribution

thresholds are better sought from long-tailed distributions. As illustrated below, the studentized residuals in these kinds of data often more closely follow a logistic pattern or occasionally something between the logistic and cauchy distributions. To accommodate this empirical reality, we propose the following somewhat crude criteria using a pair of fixed thresholds:

- Classify any measurement or nominal value with a studentized residual greater than 4 as a probable outlier, and any studentized residual greater than 8 as a definite/extreme outlier.

The justification for these thresholds can be seen in Tukey’s box plot outlier screening technique. In Tukey’s version, outliers are flagged whenever an observation lies beyond a multiple of the interquartile range (IQR) either below the lower or above the upper hinge of the box plot, where the hinges represent essentially the lower and upper data quartiles. For standard normal data, Tukey suggestion of a multiplier of 1.5 for flagging ‘mild’ outliers leads to an absolute outlier threshold value of 2.7, which should ostensibly capture all but roughly one percent of a normally-distributed non-outlying population. ‘Extreme’ outliers are flagged using a multiplier of 3 instead of 1.5. This leads to a threshold of 4.7, designed to capture much more than 99.99% of non-outliers.

Applying this same logic to the logistic distribution yields a modified pair of absolute thresholds: 4.4 and 7.7. In the cauchy case, similar absolute thresholds would be 4 and 7. We round these to 4 and 8 as a working solution, recognizing that the standard logistic or possibly the standard cauchy are merely approximate models of the studentized residuals encountered in practice.

The empirical data on which MCOID has been tested also tend to justify the use of, especially, the logistic distribution as a model for the studentized residuals. At all of the sites considered in the comparative study described below, quantile-quantile plots of the externally-studentized residuals more closely matched the logistic than either the normal, Student’s t with $(n-3)$ df, or cauchy distributions. Two examples of these comparative Q-Q plots are shown in **Figure 17** and **Figure 18** in the Appendix.

As a final safeguard, instead of excluding flagged outliers from subsequent analysis, MCOID is designed to *down-weight* flagged values as a function of their studentized residual distance from the trend. This provides some insurance against misclassification in either direction (i.e., false positive or false negative outlier outcomes). True outliers tend to receive smaller weights than non-outliers, while weights for false outliers tend to be larger than true outliers, and more similar to non-outliers, due to a typically smaller residual distance.

In the proposed method, down-weighting is only applied to residual distances greater than the ‘probable’ outlier threshold of 4. A variety of weighting functions might be

employed. We have found good empirical performance using the well-known tri-cube function (Loader, 1999) combined with a scaled half-logistic kernel.

3 Some Examples

MCOID has been tested for outlier screening on thousands of environmental time series. Generally, it works well, matching intuitive perceptions of likely outliers, whether among detected observations or non-detects with unusually high reporting limits. MCOID also handles large or small fractions of left-censored measurements with similar aplomb. Several discrete examples are pictured in the **Appendix** in **Figures 1** through **16**. In each case, the top panel shows the time series, spline trend, prediction band, and status of each measurement, along with dashed demarcations (in purple) of the boundary for definite/extreme outliers. The bottom panel shows the studentized residuals and fixed thresholds used to classify each value. Note in these plots that CUSP refers to probable/mild outliers and OUT refers to definite/extreme outliers.

4 Comparison Study

As an empirical test of the MCOID method, we compared it on a range of environmental time series datasets to six alternate strategies. The methods included commonly employed univariate outlier tests as well as a variation of the MCOID algorithm:

1. **Adhoc**. A univariate outlier screening test that classifies any value larger than 2 standard deviations in absolute value from the mean as a probable outlier, and any value larger than 3 standard deviations as a definite/extreme outlier. Any non-detects are imputed to half their reporting limits (RL).
2. **Tukey**. Univariate box plot outlier screen first suggested in (Tukey, 1977), which classifies probable/mild outliers as any value more than 1.5 times the interquartile range (IQR) below the lower hinge or 1.5 times the IQR above the upper hinge of the box plot. Definite/extreme outliers are flagged when more than 3 times the IQR below or above the box plot edges. Any non-detects are imputed to half their reporting limits (RL).
3. **Tukey-LOP**. Tukey box plot screen applied to data that have first been ‘normalized’ using a simplification of the Box-Cox transformation method (Box & Cox, 1964) known as the Ladder of Powers (LOP) (Helsel et al., 2020),

first introduced in (Velleman & Hoaglin, 1981). Tukey’s box plot outlier screen is applied to data first scaled by the transformation exhibiting the largest normal quantile-quantile plot correlation.

4. **Grubbs.** A univariate outlier discordancy test (Barnett & Lewis, 1994) historically recommended by EPA (USEPA, 2009) and first proposed in (Grubbs, 1950). Any non-detects are imputed to half their reporting limits (RL). Probable outliers are classified as those significant at the 5% level, while definite/extreme outliers are defined by significance at the 1% level.
5. **Rosner.** An iterative univariate outlier test proposed in (Rosner, 1975), and recommended in EPA guidance (USEPA, 2009). An improved and expanded computational algorithm, allowing for single as well as multiple outlier identification, was introduced by Cameron (Cameron, 2019). Any non-detects are imputed to half their reporting limits (RL). Probable outliers are classified as those significant at the 5% level, while definite/extreme outliers are defined by significance at the 1% level.
6. **MCOID-Tukey.** A variation of the MCOID algorithm whereby Tukey’s outlier box plot screen is applied to the externally-studentized residuals instead of using fixed outlier thresholds.

All seven methods were run on data from 10 different environmental monitoring sites, representing a total of over 50,000 groundwater measurements. Since the number of actual outliers is unknown, and can only be qualitatively judged by visual inspection, all six alternate methods were assessed *relative* to the MCOID outcomes on the same data. More specifically, relative ‘misclassification’ rates were computed, such that an over-classification was recorded whenever an alternate method flagged an outlier (either probable or definite/extreme) but MCOID did not, and vice-versa for under-classification. The relative misclassification rates are shown in **Table 4** in the **Appendix**.

Table 4 clearly indicates that the worst performing method (relative to MCOID) is the MCOID-Tukey variant. Across the sites tested, at least 5-9% of all the measurements were flagged as outliers by MCOID-Tukey, but as *non-outliers* by MCOID. The next worst methods were Tukey’s box plot screen applied to either the raw data or a ‘normalized’ transformation of the same measurements. The method that most closely matched MCOID was the univariate Rosner’s test, though at some sites around 2% of the observations were still over-classified by Rosner as probable or definite/extreme outliers. None of the alternate methods exhibited substantial under-classification relative to MCOID.

In general, baseline rates of MCOID outlier classification fluctuated near 1-2% in this study. Example outcomes are shown in **Table 1**, **Table 2**, and **Table 3**. Some additional graphical comparisons are shown in **Figure 19**, **Figure 20**, **Figure 21**,

Figure 22, and **Figure 23** in the **Appendix**. These examples illustrate cases where MCOID outperformed the alternate methods, either by avoiding misclassification of non-outliers or occasionally flagging outliers that other methods tended to miss.

Table 1: CUF Site Comparative Outlier Results

METHOD	IN ^a	CUSP ^b	OUT ^c	CNT ^d
adhoc	98.0	1.2	0.9	4,782
grubbs	95.3	0.4	4.4	4,782
mcoid	99.4	0.4	0.2	4,782
mcoid.tukey	90.2	3.7	6.0	4,782
rosner	97.1	0.4	2.5	4,782
tukey	93.0	1.9	5.1	4,782
tukey.lop	93.7	1.8	4.4	4,782

^aIN = Not Statistical Outlier

^bCUSP = Probable or 5% Level Statistical Outlier

^cOUT = Definite/Extreme or 1% Level Statistical Outlier

^dCNT = Number of Observations

Table 2: SAN Site Comparative Outlier Results

METHOD	IN ^a	CUSP ^b	OUT ^c	CNT ^d
adhoc	97.5	1.0	1.5	5,698
grubbs	97.2	0.3	2.4	5,698
mcoid	98.9	1.0	0.1	5,698
mcoid.tukey	93.2	2.6	4.2	5,698
rosner	98.3	0.2	1.4	5,698
tukey	94.7	2.2	3.2	5,698
tukey.lop	96.9	2.1	1.0	5,698

^aIN = Not Statistical Outlier

METHOD	IN ^a	CUSP ^b	OUT ^c	CNT ^d
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^bCUSP = Probable or 5% Level Statistical Outlier

^cOUT = Definite/Extreme or 1% Level Statistical Outlier

^dCNT = Number of Observations

Table 3: CSU Site Comparative Outlier Results

METHOD	IN ^a	CUSP ^b	OUT ^c	CNT ^d
adhoc	96.5	2.3	1.2	4,389
grubbs	94.7	1.5	3.9	4,389
mcoid	97.7	1.9	0.4	4,389
mcoid.tukey	90.1	4.4	5.5	4,389
rosner	98.0	0.7	1.3	4,389
tukey	92.9	3.3	3.9	4,389
tukey.lop	94.3	3.4	2.3	4,389

^aIN = Not Statistical Outlier

^bCUSP = Probable or 5% Level Statistical Outlier

^cOUT = Definite/Extreme or 1% Level Statistical Outlier

^dCNT = Number of Observations

5 Limitations and Future Work

MCOID works well in practice, but is not foolproof. Apparent non-outliers are sometimes misclassified as outliers, particularly near the beginning or end of an irregular time series at which there is greater relative data sparsity (i.e., lower measurement frequency) combined with a steeper local slope. This may be an inherent or at least ubiquitous limitation of the methodology.

While MCOID provides favorable outcomes in this study compared to the tested alternate methods, it should be compared against a larger range of alternatives, including the use of recommended univariate outlier tests applied to ‘normalized’ mea-

surements or perhaps against such tests applied to the studentized trend residuals. Most standard outlier tests presume a normal, non-outlying reference population.

As the present study is empirical, further work might involve a systematic comparison of simulated data, using contaminated data with varying but known proportions or numbers of outliers.

6 Conclusion

The Monte Carlo Outlier Identification (MCOID) screening technique has been applied to thousands of environmental datasets, particularly groundwater time series. ‘Obvious’ outliers are nearly always flagged, suggesting the method has good power. Probable outliers are usually flagged and downweighted as well, but not typically at the expense of misclassifying non-outliers.

The key advantages of MCOID include:

- It may be the first method specifically structured to identify outliers in environmental time series in the presence of large levels of left-censoring (i.e., non-detects).
- The MCOID algorithm is programmed in R and quite speedy, easily handling bulk data processing.
- No data are ever excluded, merely flagged and downweighted.
- It has the ability to handle high levels of left-censoring while still providing good accuracy.

7 References

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Appendix

Table 4: Relative Misclassification Rates (%)

site	N	mcoid-tukey		adhoc		tukey		tukey-lop		grubbs		rosner	
		over ^a	under ^b	over	under	over	under	over	under	over	under	over	under
san	6,231	5.15	0	1.30	0.06	4.06	0.11	2.20	0.40	1.60	0.13	0.63	0.16
cuf.still	4,782	9.20	0	1.61	0.15	6.50	0.10	5.81	0.15	4.37	0.15	2.43	0.15
cuf.drystack	5,492	9.21	0	1.71	0.20	6.21	0.20	5.68	0.31	3.55	0.27	1.88	0.29
csu.ccr	4,389	7.68	0	2.01	0.77	5.47	0.59	4.44	1.03	3.67	0.62	0.84	1.07
alf	7,853	6.01	0	2.02	0.31	4.16	0.20	3.23	0.38	1.35	0.37	0.43	0.42
paf.gypsum	5,640	5.30	0	1.54	0.11	2.71	0.09	2.46	0.27	1.08	0.11	0.48	0.16
paf.peabody	6,468	5.67	0	1.93	0.20	4.02	0.11	3.42	0.19	2.04	0.19	0.74	0.20
que	4,234	5.90	0	2.15	0.35	5.90	0.28	5.15	0.31	3.21	0.19	0.87	0.33
kif.still	2,582	9.06	0	1.90	0.15	6.31	0.12	6.20	0.23	5.03	0.12	2.21	0.15
kif.sluiice	3,612	8.69	0	1.72	0.25	6.17	0.14	5.37	0.14	4.68	0.14	2.44	0.19

^aover = Pct Tagged Outliers by Method but not by MCOID (over-classification)

^bunder = Pct Tagged Outliers by MCOID but not by Method (under-classification)

Figure 1: ALF Site MCOID Plots

Temporal Outlier Screening for Barium at ALF-202

Temporal Outlier Screening for Barium at ALF-202

Figure 2: ALF Site MCOID Plots

Figure 3: ALF Site MCOID Plots

Figure 4: ALF Site MCOID Plots

Figure 5: QUE Site MCOID Plots

Figure 6: QUE Site MCOID Plots

Figure 7: QUE Site MCOID Plots

Figure 8: SAN Site MCOID Plots

Figure 9: SAN Site MCOID Plots

Figure 10: KIF Site MCOID Plots

Figure 11: KIF Site MCOID Plots

Figure 12: PAF Site MCOID Plots

Figure 13: PAF Site MCOID Plots

Temporal Outlier Screening for Barium at CUF-212

Figure 14: CUF Site MCOID Plots

Figure 15: CUF Site MCOID Plots

Temporal Outlier Screening for pH at CUF-208

Temporal Outlier Screening for pH at CUF-208

Figure 16: CUF Site MCOID Plots

Figure 17: KIF Site, Residual Q-Q Plots

Figure 18: QUE Site, Residual Q-Q Plots

Figure 19: KIF Site, Well 6AR

Flagged Temporal Outliers for Molybdenum at AD-1 by Method

Figure 20: KIF Site, Well AD-1

Flagged Temporal Outliers for Molybdenum at 93-2R by Method

Figure 21: CUF Site, Well 93-2R

Figure 22: ALF Site, Well ALF-206

Figure 23: SAN Site, Well MW-1